

Addition Compounds of Phosphoryl Chloride and Bromide with Tertiary Amines

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Complexes of phosphoryl chloride and bromide have been prepared with pyridine, β - and γ -picolines, quinoline, isoquinoline and piperidine. They have 1 : 3-(POX_3 : base) stoichiometry except for the complexes of phosphoryl bromide with pyridine and piperidine which have 1 : 4-stoichiometry. Structures of these complexes have been discussed in the light of their infrared spectra and molar conductance data.

Phosphoryl chloride and bromide form addition compounds with metal halides^{1,2}. Infrared spectra^{1,3} do not favour their ionic nature and indicate the coordination of oxygen atom of phosphoryl halides to metal halides. But a study of the solutions of metal halides in phosphoryl halides^{4,5} has indicated the presence of ion pairs such as $\text{POX}_2^+ \cdot \text{POX}_4 \cdot \text{A}^-$ (A = metal halides). However the interaction of bases with phosphoryl halides has not been reported except that 1 : 1⁶ and 1 : 2⁷ addition compounds of phosphoryl chloride with pyridine, and a complex of phosphoryl chloride with dimethylformamide⁸ are known. The preparation of the complexes of phosphoryl chloride and bromide with tertiary nitrogen bases is being reported here. Their infrared spectra and molar conductance have been studied to throw some light on their structure.

EXPERIMENTAL

Petroleum ether, carbon tetrachloride and benzene (all BDH. AnalaR) were further purified by the usual methods. Tertiary amines were purified and dried as already described⁹. Phosphoryl chloride was repeatedly distilled in an all glass apparatus and the middle fraction collected for use. Phosphoryl bromide was prepared by the interaction of phosphorus (III) bromide and phosphorus (V) oxide¹⁰.

Preparation of the complexes : The complexes of phosphoryl chloride and bromide with tertiary amines have been prepared by adding ice cold solution of phosphoryl halide in petroleum ether to an ice cold solution of the base in the same solvent in different stoichiometric ratios. Solid compounds which precipitated out on their mixing were filtered, repeatedly washed with petroleum ether and dried under vacuum.

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The halogen content of the complexes was estimated by Volhard's method¹¹ and nitrogen was estimated by microanalytical techniques. Molar conductance of milimolar solutions of complexes in nitrobenzene was calculated from their specific conductance. Infrared spectra of the complexes have been examined as nujol mulls employing a Perkin-Elmer-337 infrared spectrophotometer. Liquid complexes have been examined as thin liquid films in NaCl or KBr plates.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phosphoryl chloride and bromide react exothermally with tertiary amines to give solid addition compounds. It is evident from analytical data (Table I) that most of the complexes have 1 : 3 stoichiometry except for the adducts of phosphoryl bromide with pyridine and piperidine which have 1 : 4 stoichiometry. Except for a feeble solubility in nitrobenzene, the complexes are insoluble in most of the common organic solvents. Molar conductance of $10^{-3}M$ solutions of these complexes in nitrobenzene (Table I) indicate that the complexes are almost non-electrolytes in their solutions in nitrobenzene as molar conductance required for 1 : 1 electrolyte in this solvent is 20 to 30 $\text{cm}^2 \text{ohm}^{-1} \text{mole}^{-1}$ ¹².

TABLE I

Analysis, molar conductance, physical state and melting points of the complexes of tertiary amines with phosphoryl halides

Complex	Colour	M.P. °C	Found %		Calculated %		Molar conductance**
			X*	N	X	N	
POCl ₃ .3 pyridine	White solid	84	27.3	10.2	27.3	10.7	1.36
POCl ₃ .3-β-picoline	Yellow solid	48	25.3	9.2	24.6	9.7	4.40
POCl ₃ .3-γ-picoline	White solid	121	24.4	9.9	24.6	9.7	9.90
POCl ₃ .3 quinoline	White	—	19.65	7.2	19.7	7.7	1.23
POCl ₃ .3 isoquinoline	White	175	19.54	7.4	19.7	7.2	5.20
POCl ₃ .3 piperidine	White	212	26.2	10.4	26.0	10.6	2.60
POBr ₃ .4 pyridine	White	164	38.1	9.1	39.8	9.2	—
POBr ₃ .3 γ-picoline	Cream	85 (decomp.)	42.0	7.3	42.2	7.4	—
POBr ₃ .3 quinoline	Yellowish white	—	35.2	—	35.5	—	—
POBr ₃ .3 isoquinoline	Light yellow	184	34.8	6.0	35.5	6.2	—
POBr ₃ .4 piperidine	White	225	39.3	8.6	38.3	8.9	—

* = halogen.

** $\text{cm}^2 \text{ohm}^{-1} \text{mole}^{-1}$ ($10^{-3} M$ solutions in nitrobenzene).

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Infrared spectra of the complexes are recorded from 4000–400 cm^{-1} in Table II. The spectral data indicate that the absorption frequencies of the base molecules as well as those of the phosphoryl halides are perturbed on complex formation. The C—H stretching frequency of the base molecules which absorbs at 3050–2950 cm^{-1} spectral region shifts to the lower spectral region in the complexes (Table II) which is an indication of the coordination of the base through its nitrogen atom¹³⁻¹⁵. The significant frequencies of the bases lying in

TABLE II

Significant infrared spectral bands of tertiary amines and their complexes with phosphoryl chloride

	$\nu(\text{C—H})$	$\nu(\text{C} \cdots \text{C}) + \nu(\text{C} \cdots \text{N})$			Ring vibrations			$\nu(\text{P}=\text{O})^\dagger$ ($\text{P—Cl})^\ddagger$	
Pyridine (P)	3005 s	1583 m,	1527 s,	1483 s,	1005 s,	600 s	405 s	—	—
$\text{POCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{P}$	2850 bs	1630 m,	1600 vs,	1525 s,	1020 s,	620 m,	430 m	1200 s	470
$\text{POBr}_3 \cdot 4\text{P}$	2900 bs	1635 m,	1600 vs,	1530 s,	1015 s,	625 m,	428 m	1230 s	—
γ -picoline (γ)	2955 s	1595 s,	1556 s,	1490 s,	513 s,	485 s	—	—	—
$\text{POCl}_3 \cdot 3\gamma$	2850 bs	1630 m,	1600 vs,	1550 s	540 m,	495 m	—	1250 s,	470 m
$\text{POBr}_3 \cdot 3\gamma$	2900 bs	1625 s,	1600 vs,	1555 m,	445 m,	498 w	—	1200 s	—
Quinoline (Q)	3020 s	1630 m,	1580 s,	1550 s,	—	—	—	—	—
$\text{POCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Q}$	2950 bs	1650 s,	1595 s,	1555 s,	—	—	—	—	—
$\text{POBr}_3 \cdot 3\text{Q}$	2920 bs	1650 s,	1600 s,	1550 s,	—	—	—	—	—
Isoquinoline (I)	3050 s	1630 m,	1590	1500 s,	—	—	—	—	—
$\text{POCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{I}$	2800 bs	1645 sm,	1615 s,	1590 s.	—	—	—	—	—
$\text{POBr}_3 \cdot 3\text{I}$	2800 bs	1650 s,	1620 s,	1570 s,	—	—	—	—	—
		Piperidine (Pip)	Assignment	$\text{POCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Pip}$	$\text{POBr}_3 \cdot 4\text{Pip}$				
		3290 s	$\nu(\text{N—H})$	3140 bs	3150 s				
		2925 s } 2840 m } 2795 m } 2720 m }	$\nu(\text{C—H})$	2810 2750 s	2750 s				
		1470 s } 1445 s }	(H—C—H) bending	1460 s	1460 s				
		1385 s } 1330 s } 1320 s } 1280 s } 1260 s }	(H—C—C) wagg	1390 s 1355 s — 1315 s 1290 s	1390 s 1360 s — 1295 m				
		1120 s } 940 s } 860 s }	Ring vib.	1155 m 1035 s 925 s	1160 s 1030 m 930 s				
		822 s	(H—N—C) def.	860 s	860 s				

$\dagger \nu(\text{P}=\text{O})$ of POCl_3 and POBr_3 is at 1290 and 1260 cm^{-1} respectively.

$\ddagger \nu(\text{P—Cl})$ of POCl_3 is at 485 cm^{-1} .

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the 1600–1400 cm^{-1} region due to $\text{C} \equiv \text{C}$ and $\text{C} \equiv \text{N}$ stretching vibrations shift to higher region in those of the complexes. The above observation is in accord with the infrared spectra of coordination complexes of these bases with a variety of other acceptors. The ring vibrations of the amines at the 400–600 cm^{-1} region (Table II) also shift to the higher region in the spectra of the complexes. For instance, the bands of pyridine at 405 and 600 cm^{-1} shift to 422 and 620 cm^{-1} respectively in the spectra of the complexes which has already been pointed out by Paul *et al.*^{16,17} and Gill *et al.*¹⁸ to be the criteria of coordination of pyridine through nitrogen.

The spectral perturbation of piperidine molecule on formation of complexes with phosphoryl chloride and bromide are comparable to those for piperidine hydrochloric acid complex¹⁴. There is a large spectral shift to lower region in $\nu(\text{N-H})$ of piperidine. The comparable shift of $\nu(\text{N-H})$ of piperidine in its complexes with phosphoryl halides and hydrochloric acid indicate that the coordination of piperidine is very strong and the complexes are very stable. The stability of these complexes is evident from their melting points (Table II).

$\text{P} = \text{O}$ stretching frequency of phosphoryl halides²⁰ shifts to a lower region in the spectra of complexes. A similar shift of $\nu(\text{C} = \text{O})$ of acetic anhydride in its adducts with tertiary amines have been noticed¹⁹. Since no Lewis acid has been used for coordination with phosphoryl halides, this shift of $\nu(\text{P} = \text{O})$ indicates the polarization of $\text{P} = \text{O}$ bond when phosphoryl halides combine with bases. This shift can be explained on the basis of a strong bonding between the phosphorus atom of phosphoryl halide and the nitrogen atom of the base. The relative shift of $\nu(\text{P} = \text{O})$ of phosphoryl halide with a reference base is correlated to their acceptor strength which is as $\text{POBr}_3 < \text{POCl}_3$. The $\nu(\text{P} = \text{O})$ shift is the largest in piperidine complexes.

The P-Cl stretching frequency of phosphoryl chloride²⁰ is only slightly perturbed in the spectra of the complexes which indicates that P-Cl bond is not directly involved in the change of structure and therefore the representation of the structure of the complex as $[\text{POX}_2(\beta)_3]^+ \cdot \text{X}^-$ is not justified. This also gets support from the behaviour of phosphoryl halides in disulphuric acid²¹. Similarly the representation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes already known^{6,7} as $[(\text{POCl}_2\text{Py})]^+ \text{Cl}^-$ and

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